

Climateurope2

Climateurope2 platform

Deliverable 7.5

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Climateurope2

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About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information are fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate-neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this by providing climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and need for climate information have seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. Various activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

In line with the project goals, a need was established to develop an interactive platform and support service for the benefit of the European climate services community, to facilitate the access to guidelines, good practices and recommendations from the project, and the interaction with the scientists involved in the project. The Climateurope2 platform offers a mechanism for user participation, with the possibility of providing feedback on the standardisation processes and the recommended guidelines and good practices, access to a glossary on climate services, and the visualisation of the community engaged in the project.

Executive Summary

This Deliverable describes the approach towards, and the actually released final version, of the Climateurope2 platform. Previous versions have been distributed to a selected user board within the CE2 project for gathering feedback. Following this feedback, an update to the original platform's design was implemented, culminating in the final stable version of the platform described here. The platform is shown here via screenshots using three user flows that have three levels of user rights (public user, CE2 community basic and CE2 community approved). The main sections of the platform are *co-create*, *explore*, *connect* and *analytics*. The *co-create* section allows registered users (with sufficient rights) to publish and discuss drafts of guidelines and good practices until a consensus is reached and they are ready for public access. *Explore* facilitates access to the final versions of the project documents, best practices, glossary terms, training modules and key messages via an interactive and user-friendly repository. *Connect* hosts information in a catalogue

about members of the climate services community in the network to identify connections and flow of information among actors in the network. And finally, *analytics* includes the Visual Analytics Dashboard, which enables users to browse CE2 content, as well as the broader context of what is being published on climate services across the world from multiple channels (news, companies, public sector, etc.).

Keywords

Climateurope2, platform, climate services, best practices, guidelines, co-create, analytics, explore, connect, network, repository.

1 Functionalities Climateurope2 platform

1.1 General introduction

The Climateurope2 (CE2) platform (<https://platform.climateurope2.eu/>) supports internal discussions and engages the climate services community by making guidelines, good practices and recommendations regarding climate services widely available, easy to find and usable during and after the project's lifetime. The platform is accessible from the Climateurope2 website and, in a secure environment, allows registered users (with sufficient rights) to publish and discuss drafts of guidelines and good practices until a consensus is reached and they are ready for public access. Publicly, it facilitates access to the final versions of documents, glossary terms, training modules and key messages via an interactive and user-friendly repository. This is not to be confused with the 'project resource repository' that is for internal use only.

The platform's **co-create** section enables Climateurope2 members to enter the documents (guidelines, standards, good practices) with standardised metadata (title, tags, etc.). The **explore** section showcases the documents and allows for faceted searching and filtering. The **analytics** section provides visualisation services to explore content via the *CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard* and oversee the content collection process, assess the quality of the extracted metadata and perform searches that further enrich the application. The **connect** section hosts information in a catalogue about members in the network to identify connections and flow of information among actors in the network. The platform is designed to engage specialised audiences and stakeholders, while also serving as one of the project's outputs and a collection of materials for wider dissemination.

1.1.1 Main objectives

The main objectives of the Climateurope2 platform are:

- To provide an interactive and user-friendly repository that provides easy access to good practices, training modules, key messages, glossary terms, recommendations and standardisation processes of climate services, and encourages community engagement and knowledge co-production;
- To connect and create a community (to incentivise people using the platform);
- To have a clear and intuitive navigation structure, making it easy for users to find the information on climate services that they need.

1.1.2 Design process

Starting from what was described in D7.3, and following the Beta release of the Climateurope2 platform, it was distributed to a selected user board within the CE2 project for gathering a second round of feedback. The platform has been tested through interviews with various project partners, and insights obtained from these interactions have been considered to inform the proposal of a new platform design. A proposal for design changes followed, affecting tags and buttons, the architecture of the information, PDF document accessibility, format of the footer, breadcrumbs, tooltips, the implementation of a more guided user experience (improving onboarding and making the landing page more intuitive) as well as the addition of new features such as cards to display particular items for the glossary and the key messages. Additional feedback from the consortium on the changes that required more effort was gathered through email (using a shared feedback document). A new differentiated section was created for the Visual Analytics dashboard, initially embedded in the 'explore' section, to differentiate information uploaded by the climate services community from the broader set of data sources. For the dashboard itself, the development efforts focused on simplifying the navigational structure (reducing the number of primary tabs and offering additional options through secondary

tabs) and on using generative AI to summarise the results. Selected topics or metadata attributes segment the created summaries. Following this new design, the final stable version of the platform was developed, which is described here.

1.1.3 Technical implementation

Various updates have been made to the Climateurope2 platform since the Beta release described in D7.3:

- Implementation of the new design:
 - Redistributed the main sections of the platform to four different ones: co-create, explore, analytics and connect;
 - Restructuring of the homepage, including a direct link to the document library;
 - Added a separate page for Glossary terms;
 - Added a separate page for the yearly key messages;
 - The published documents are now embedded in the webpage;
- Improved commenting, filtering and versioning;
- Rework of the co-create steps to be more intuitive on how to collaborate on the documents. This includes additional information for certain elements and reduction of the number of steps;
- Each document version in a co-create entry is tagged accordingly. This means that when a document is first uploaded in the co-create it is labeled version 1. When feedback is received, the user might want to upload a new version, which is then labeled version 2. Comments now display which document version they refer to.
- When a new file version is uploaded to co-create and linked to a published document, it is now correctly associated as the next version. At the same time, visual indicators show the relationship between the old and new versions.
- Updates to the user profile information and option to toggle visibility in the connect section of the platform.
- Improved notifications and access requests, where users are notified via email when they are added as co-authors or collaborators, or when they receive comments. The author also receives an email when a user requests access to their document.
- When external users request access to co-create, administrators receive the application for review.
- Changes were made to the filtering, searching and authentication & error handling.
- Work on the embedded analytics dashboard has focused on improving the user experience, including a revised navigational system for both the embedded and standalone versions of the dashboard, as well as AI summaries that enable users to more quickly grasp key results.

The platform is a custom-developed web application built using Symfony PHP (modules), featuring a database for user management, a database for metadata best practices, and a front-end input form that allows (co)authors to submit their publications. These publications include good practices extracted from the project Deliverables by experts. The practices can include different parts of a climate service workflow, e.g. from raw data to a data product. Each good practice publication follows a metadata template and receives its own persistent Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), which can be found using a repository's search entry, enabled by using relevant keywords. Visual analytics capabilities developed by partner WebLyzard are embedded into the platform to provide aggregate representations of search results, to identify stakeholders and opinion leaders, and to assess the impact of events and communication activities. The visual analytics capabilities are available as widgets embedded into the platform and as a standalone CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard, providing more advanced analytic features to explore and navigate climate service-related content assets.

1.1.4 Navigation Structure

The main sections of the platform are co-create, explore, connect and analytics:

Co-create

The co-create section allows for collaboration in real-time on document and glossary terms consultation with multiple users and includes version control and commenting tools. The section is available to an approved selection of users (*CE2 community approved*, see 1.1.5 User rights) and facilitates interaction in the final stages of a document/glossary term. The idea is that collaborators first work together on their document or glossary term in the internal project repository or other collaborative environments before publishing a mature draft version in the co-create section. This mature draft version can then be viewed here by relevant collaborators (chosen by the (co)author) that can provide feedback with comments under the document or glossary term. Based on the received feedback, the mature draft version can then be revised and re-uploaded, which can be an iterative approach and repeated as many times as required. Once the final revision has taken place and the document or glossary term is approved by all collaborators and (co)authors, it can be published to the explore section.

Explore

The explore section is the main section of the Climateurope2 platform that contains the published documents and glossary terms from the co-create section and a set of training modules and yearly key messages related to climate services, developed by the Climateurope2 project but also the wider community. This section is open for all users without having to register (*Public user*, see 1.1.5 User rights):

- The **Documents** contain information on access guidelines, good practices, use cases, and other relevant materials through an easy-to-use catalogue.
- The **Key Messages** are a yearly project output resulting from feedback provided by all WPs, based on the second annual reporting template. Structured around the decision tree and 25 criteria/requirements, WP1 analysed and mined the information to develop a set of updated key insights derived from the learnings of the project's second year. WP7 further developed a layout summarising the key messages which are included for 2024 and 2025 as a separate page under the document library.
- The **Glossary** included as a separate page, provides definitions of key terms related to climate services. It serves as a reference point for all users to create a shared understanding of terminology across disciplines and stakeholder groups. Each entry is established after various in-depth discussions in the project related to climate service quality, performance, impact, effectiveness, and success. The glossary contributes to building a common language within the Climateurope2 network and supports clarity and consistency in communication and training materials.
- The **Training Modules**, created by WP4, are included under their own page within the document library. Next to this, certain documents are tagged with the relevant training modules, e.g. an entry linked to standardization could be tagged with the training module on standardization. This tagging is done via a small symbol in the entry that links to the training module.

Connect

The connect section hosts information in a catalogue about members in the network to identify connections and flow of information among actors in the network. It also facilitates interaction among members, by introducing a chatting functionality. This section is only accessible for registered users (*CE2 community basic*, see 1.1.5 User rights).

Analytics

The analytics page includes an embedded “LITE” version of the CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard (loading with a predefined bookmark to yield search results on a query for “climate services”), to enable users to browse CE2 content as well as the broader context of what is being published about climate services across geographic regions and channels (news, companies, public sector, etc.). The main navigation within the LITE Dashboard includes multiple tabs at the bottom of the screen to switch between the different modes to display the results, and a dropdown in the right sidebar to select the most suitable color-coding for the task at hand. In addition to the embedded version, geared towards casual users and the public, registered users can access the standalone PRO¹ version of the CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard.

¹ <https://climate.weblyzard.com/pro>

Figure 1 - Climateurope2 Platform navigation structure.

1.1.5 User rights

The platform supports different users, and has three different levels of User Rights, allowing for placing access restrictions on different parts of the platform.

Public user

This user is not logged in, but can access published documents in the explore section and read related comments. This user gets access to the “LITE” version of the CE2 Visual Analytics dashboard, and a selected set of content sources to be determined by CE2 partners.

CE2 community basic

This user is registered via the platform and gets access to the same features as the public user. Additionally, this user gets access to the connect section and the professional version of the CE2 dashboard, with more advanced analytic capabilities and additional content sources. He/she can place comments on published documents and can request to become CE2 community approved member, which grants access to the co-create section.

CE2 community approved

This user is part of the Climateurope2 project or an approved CE2 community member and has the same rights as the CE2 community user. This user gets access to the co-create section and can comment on the documents that they brought in as an author or where they are included as collaborators.

Section/Features	Public User	CE2 Basic	CE2 Approved
Explore	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Analytics – LITE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Analytics – PRO	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Comment on documents	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Connect	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Co-create	-	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Table 1 - Climateurope2 Platform User Rights.

2 User flows

This chapter showcases the Climateurope2 platform from the perspective of the three different user groups listed above. It is available at <https://platform.climateurope2.eu/>.

2.1 Public user

1. The user can explore the homepage to get familiar with the platform's features and options. Here, the main sections, co-create, explore, connect, and analytics are clearly visible and shortly explained. The co-create and connect sections are not available. Users who do not have an account yet can click the Connect section to register. When clicking on the co-create section, the user is first asked to register and afterwards required to request approval to become a CE2 community-approved member in order to access the co-create section.

Figure 2 - Climateurope2 Platform homepage.

2. The user can navigate to the analytics section with the embedded LITE version of the CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard. The tab structure at the bottom of the screen couples the various

representations into six distinct groups: (1) Documents and stories, (2) AI summaries, (3) Keyword associations in the form of a tag cloud, a keyword graph or a cluster map, (4) Trend chart and stream graph, (5) geographic map, and (6) source list include reach and impact metrics. The colour-coding of the screenshot shown in Fig. 2 classifies the results by source. Other options available via the dropdown are “Sentiment” (positive vs. negative), “Recency” (segmented into four quartiles), “Associations” and “Topics”. The latter allows users to specify search queries to sub-segment the results on the fly, or to access pre-configured bookmarks that can be created or edited using the PRO version of the dashboard (see below).

Figure 3 - The integrated Climateurope2 Dashboard shows the regional distribution of climate service-related online publications (Jan - July 2025) from companies (pink), non-profit organisations (brown), the public sector (green), news organisations (yellow), as well as universities and research centres (blue).

3. Within the explore section, the user is able to see all published documents.

Climateurope2
PLATFORM

Search documents by type, author, name

My Profile

About Actions Contact Feedback

> All Documents

See all documentation

Our document section is a valuable resource for anyone seeking to stay up-to-date on the latest research and developments in climate services. Here, you can find a wide range of documents, including guidelines, vocabulary, reports, papers, and presentations, all of which are available for download.

Glossary

See our expanding list of climate related terms.

Explore >

Training

Browse our training materials.

Explore >

Key messages

The annual Climateurope2 synthesis report.

Explore >

Found 4 document(s).

Filters

Search by author

Search by unit of analysis

Search by document type

Search by spatial domain

Reset filters

XD	Governance tools identified in Deliverable D2.1	Reports	Delivery mode and evaluation
X Domingo 2025-02-22			
XD	List of governance tools related to Artificial Intelligence.	Others	Delivery mode and evaluation
X Domingo 2025-01-20			
MB	Climate services components identified by Climateurope2	Best Practices	Others
Marina Baldissera Pacchetti 2024-09-24		Climate Services as a whole	Standards
SZ	Climateurope2 Glossary	Glossary	Climate Services as a whole
Saioa Zorita 2024-09-24			

Figure 4 - Climateurope2 Platform documents.

- The user can search for the relevant document, using the search bar or filters for the list of resources available. Once the document is found, it can be opened to obtain more information, display the abstract, have access to the embedded document and download it.

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PLATFORM

Search documents by type, author, name

My Profile

About Actions Contact Feedback

All Documents > Climate services components identified by climateurope2

Key Info Document

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Junior Research Engineer
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Researcher
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DOI
No DOI assigned

Upload date
2024 Sep 24

Last update
2024 Sep 24
16:09

Priority
Medium

Status
In progress

Tags
Climate Services as a whole
Others
Best Practices
Standards

Spatial Domain
European

Version
V1

Source
No source provided

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Climate services components identified by Climateurope2

Abstract

Climate services components identified through a series of co-production workshops held between January and February 2023 by Climateurope2 Consortium participants. This document also provides a brief description of the component identification process. These components serve as an initial starting point to identify aspects of climate services that are amenable and mature enough for standardisation, and are an attempt to provide some boundaries and at the same time break the complexity of climate services into recognisable sets of data, processes, products and actors.

[Click here to read the complete version](#)

1 van 2 Automatisch zoomen

Climate services components identified by Climateurope2

1. Introduction

Climate Services involve the provision of climate information in such a way as to assist decision-making. The service includes appropriate engagement from users and providers, is based on scientifically credible information and expertise, has an effective access mechanism and responds to users needs. Given the complexity of climate services and their landscape, Climateurope2 proposed to break the conceptualisation of climate services into a set of high-level components for which questions about best practices, guidance and standardisation can be addressed individually, but having in mind the ties between these components.

2. How components were identified

The components of climate services have been identified through a series of workshops with all the project partners that took place between January and February 2023. These workshops were designed around the questions of the "what", the "why" and the "how" of standardisation of climate services. In these workshops participants agreed that identifying the data, processes, products, and actors that make up the key and broad components of climate services is the starting point for developing a framework for supporting standardisation.

The first workshop served as an introduction for CE2 project partners to working together, and helped clarify what approach we should take to standardisation and co-production. The second workshop allowed for some convergence on the key components of climate services. The third workshop focused on how CE2 can support climate services. This involved triangulating discussions on climate service components, standards and standardisation processes, and the work and output within different Work Packages (WPs) of CE2, especially WPs 2-5. The main outputs of the workshops relevant for this document are the following:

- There is adequate consensus on what the key components of climate services are.
- There is no consensus on the flow of the components (i.e., how different processes, products and actors are related to one another and the order they follow in a "typical" climate service), apart from the fact that a climate service starts from the users' demand.
- Different WPs and related tasks all can contribute to providing information about the different components of climate services.

3. Components of climate services

The components aim to match the breath of the definition of climate services provided above and are an attempt to provide some boundaries and at the same time break the complexity of climate services into recognisable sets of data, processes, products and actors. Climate services components, in this context, refer to the data, processes, products and actors involved in the service context and demand, as well as the design, development, implementation, uptake and evaluation of climate services. The broad components identified by project members so far are listed below, but it is important to note that the order in which the components are listed does not necessarily reflect the order in which these may appear in a climate service. Also, it is critically important to pay attention to the interconnections and interoperability across components. Moreover, throughout the lifetime of the project, CE2 members will work to harmonise this approach with other existing approaches to conceptualising the climate service value chain, as well as illustrate these components with examples.

Climateurope2 has identified four main climate services components (visualised in Fig. 1 below) that are used to structure the discussions:

- The decision-making context for which climate services must deliver value: It refers to the kind of decisions the climate service supports, including its geographical, social, and political context.
- The ecosystem of actors and co-creation processes involved: It identifies the actors involved in co-producing, evaluating, and taking up climate services, as well as the actors that might become

Figure 5 - Climateurope2 Platform document detail page. The user is able to scroll through the embedded document in a viewer. Information on the DOI, upload date, last update, priority, status, tags, spatial domain and version are provided.

- The user is able to **read** comments placed under the documents by registered users. A comment can only be **placed** once the user is registered.
- Within the explore section, the user is able to navigate to the glossary page, where all the glossary terms can be found.

Climateurope2
PLATFORM

Search documents by type, author, name

My Profile

About Actions Contact Feedback

All Documents > Glossary

Glossary

In the Climateurope2 (CE2) project, the glossary serves as a foundation for establishing a shared understanding of key terminology. The glossary is essential for fostering collaboration and ensuring that critical concepts are interpreted consistently by all project partners, which is vital for the project's successful outcome.

[Read more](#)

Found 19 glossary item(s).

Filters	Term	Definition	Source
Search by author	Impact in relation to Climate Services	It refers to the broader, long-term societal, economic, or environmental changes resulting from climate services, capturing both intended and unintended downstream effects derived from supported decision-making...	CE2 discussion
Search by unit of analysis	Effectiveness of Climate Services	It refers to the extent to which a climate service achieves its intended goals and delivers expected outcomes for users. Note 1: Example, if a climate service helps local governments understand and incorporate climate...	CE2 discussion
Search by spatial domain	Quality (in regards to climate service)	It is the degree to which a set of characteristics inherent to a climate service fulfills specified requirements. Note 1: Characteristics describe the inherent quality properties of a climate service that define its structure, outputs...	Adapted from ISO 9000
Reset filters	Performance requirement	Minimum acceptable level of a critical property Note 1: Climate services may be assessed based on several performance requirements. The outcomes of these assessments will determine different levels of climate service...	ISO 15686-1:2011, 3.19
	Requirement	A condition that must be met	CE2 discussion
	Performance of climate services	It refers to the extent to which a climate service meets its functional and operational requirements Note 1: Focus: Performance is process-oriented. It is concerned with assessing how well the service functions during its...	CE2 discussion
	Co-production	The active engagement of actors who hold different types of knowledge and resources with the aim to generate collaboratively outcomes openly defined by the facilitators of the process. Note 1: The cycle of co-production of a...	W. H. Voorberg, V. J. J. M. Bekkers, and L. G. Tummers, "A Systemati...
	Verification	Confirmation, through the provision of objective evidence, that specified requirements have been fulfilled. The term "verified" is used to designate the corresponding status.	ISO 9000
	Validation	Confirmation, through the provision of objective evidence, that the requirements for a specific intended use or application have been fulfilled Note 1 to entry: The objective evidence needed for a validation is the resul...	ISO 9000
	Uncertainty	A state of incomplete knowledge that can result from a lack of information or from disagreement about what is known or even knowable. It may have many types of sources, from imprecision in the data to ambiguously define...	https://www.ipcc.ch/re...

< 1/2 >

Figure 6 - Climateurope2 Platform glossary result page.

7. Within the explore section, the user is able to navigate to the key messages page, where the project's key messages from 2024 and 2025 are included.

Figure 7 - Climateurope2 Platform key messages detail page.

8. Within the explore section, the user is able to navigate to the training modules page, where all the project's training modules can be found. Each training module includes an embedded video visible from the platform. Documents in the library can be linked to a training module when relevant. This is then visible in the document entry.

Figure 8 - Climateurope2 Platform training modules page.

2.2 CE2 community basic

In addition to the rights of the public user, the CE2 community basic member has unlocked additional features that are showcased below. If this member wants to access the co-create page, he/she can now also request to become a CE2 community-approved member. This also involves providing more personal details and specifying motivation/expertise as a second step in the registration process.

1. If not registered yet, the user can create a new account by clicking on 'Sign up' and providing the required information.

The screenshot shows the 'Sign up' page of the Climateurope2 Platform. At the top, there is a search bar with the placeholder text 'Search documents by type, author, name' and buttons for 'Sign up' and 'Login'. Below the search bar are navigation links: 'About', 'Actions', 'Contact', and 'Feedback'. The main heading is 'Sign up to be part of our community'. To the left of the form is an illustration of a woman sitting on a stool, writing on a tablet. The form includes the following fields and options:

- Required fields are marked with '*':
- Name * (with Last name *)
- E-mail *
- Password *
- Profession
- About: Write a brief description about yourself
- I accept the [terms & conditions](#)
- I want to receive a newsletter with news, events and updates about the climate services community

At the bottom of the form, there is a blue 'Sign Up' button and a link: 'Already have an account? [Login here](#)'.

Figure 9 - Climateurope2 Platform sign up page.

2. The registered member is now able to place comments on published documents.

The screenshot shows the 'Discussion' section of the Climateurope2 Platform. The heading 'Discussion' is in a blue bar. Below it, there is a message: 'Be the first to share your thoughts by placing a comment!'. Underneath, there is a comment input area with a profile picture of a woman, a 'You' button, and a 'User' button. The input field contains the text 'Start writing your comment here...' and a blue play button icon.

Figure 10 - Climateurope2 Platform document comments.

3. In addition to the embedded version of the dashboard accessible via the "Explore" section, which is geared towards casual users and the public, members also get access to the standalone

PRO version of the CE2 Dashboard, available at <https://climate.webyzard.com/pro>. It replaces the more linear responsive design approach of the embedded version with a synchronised display of multiple widgets that show extracted metadata along multiple context dimensions (time, region, topic classifications, etc.).

The screenshot below segments climate services coverage between January and July 2025 by source, plots recent trends, clusters documents into stories, and provides advanced tooltips with the “AI Summary” feature, additional background information and rapid-drill down operations (in this case, a click on the geographic map on “Milan” summarizes the local relevant events and activities related to climate services). The ability to summarise results on the fly to convey them in a more compact format has been built into the dashboard in the main content area, as an add-on to the tooltips and in the form of a new PDF report. Currently, development efforts focus on generating labels for trend charts and story graphs using Generative AI as well, complementing the current display of keyword triples.

Figure 11 - Climateurope2 Visual Analytics Dashboard, Professional version with multiple synchronised widgets that show the search results across multiple context dimensions

- This member can also access the connect section including information in a catalogue about members in the network to identify connections and flow of information among actors in the network.

My Profile

About
Actions ▾
Contact
Feedback

[Home](#) > Network

Network

Develop the European climate service network to improve connection and engagement, encouraging open exchange of knowledge and data. Improve synergies between regional, national, European, and international activities and gain insights into the climate service community's needs for support and promotion.

Found 12 author(s).

Filters ▾

Search by author

Reset filters

Name	Research Line	Organisation	Role	Country	Contact
Paul Weerheim	Computer Science	MARIS	Software developer	VA	Send Message ▾
Tjerk Krijger	Hydraulic Engineering	MARIS	Project Engineer	NL	Send Message ▾
Fokke de Jong	climate services, climate adaptation, citizen science, sustainability, urban adaptation	Wageningen Environmental Research	Project Manager	NL	Send Message ▾
Stacey New	Climate Services & Wildfire	Met Office	Senior Climate Scientist	GB	Send Message ▾
Marta Terrado	climate services, dissemination, user engagement, ecosystem services	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	Co-leader of the Knowledge Integration team	ES	Send Message ▾
Andreas Villwock	Quality of climate services	Climate Service Center Germany at Helmholtz Centre Hereon	Staff scientist	DE	Send Message ▾
Annemarie Groot	climate adaptation	Environmental Sciences Group, Wageningen University & Research	Leader of team Climate Resilience	NL	Send Message ▾
Rutger Dankers	climate risks; climate impacts; climate services	Wageningen University & Research	Researcher; project leader	NL	Send Message ▾
Harilaos Loukos	Climate services and products development	the climate data factory	CEO	FR	Send Message ▾
Jorge Paz	Climate services	Tecnalia	Senior researcher	ES	Send Message ▾

< 1/2 >

Figure 12 - Climateurope2 Platform connect section.

2.3 CE2 community approved

In addition to the rights of the CE2 community basic member, the CE2 community approved member has unlocked additional features that are showcased below. This user is either an approved CE2 community basic member (via the request form), or part of the CE2 community (project member) that automatically unlocks this status.

1. This member is able to access the co-creation section, where users can collaborate and work together on projects and documents. Documents where the member is not included as (co)author or collaborator, will not show up on the co-create page.

The screenshot displays the 'Co-creation' section of the Climateurope2 Platform. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'About', 'Actions', 'Contact', and 'Feedback'. The main heading is 'Co-creation', followed by a brief description of the feature: 'Trigger focused discussions with the wider expert community on climate services and the standardisation of their components. This will be done through the sharing of early versions of project documents, allowing registered users to collaborate and enable the co-production of knowledge, aligning with open science practices, thus accelerating the consensus process.' A button 'Create a new document' is visible.

Below the description, there are two sections: 'Recent documents' and 'Found 8 results(s)'. The 'Recent documents' section lists three documents by Marina Baldissera Pacchetti, all dated 2025-05-26. The 'Found 8 results(s)' section lists eight documents, each with a filter button and a 'Climate Services as a whole' link. The documents are:

- Climateurope2 interim outcomes and goals for climate services (Spring 2025) (MB, 2025-05-26)
- Climateurope2 interim requirements and recommendations for climate services (Spring 2025) (MB, 2025-05-26)
- Climateurope2 interim principles for climate services (Spring 2025).pdf (MB, 2025-05-26)
- Key Messages 2025 (AL, 2025-01-27)
- Governance tools identified in Deliverable D2.1 (XD, 2025-02-22)
- List of governance tools related to Artificial Intelligence. (XD, 2025-01-20)
- Climate services components identified by Climateurope2 (MB, 2024-09-24)
- Climateurope2 Glossary (SZ, 2024-09-24)

Figure 13 - Climateurope2 Platform co-create page. The entries that are greyed out are already published in the document library. The other entries are under revision before they are ultimately published.

- The member can upload the work-in-progress document by clicking on the “Upload” button and selecting a file from the computer. The member should complete the required information, such as the document’s title, description, tags, and collaborators. If the member is listed as (co)author, he/she is able to include others as (co)author or collaborator. Note that the same steps are followed for adding a **glossary term** to the platform, albeit that the upload form contains a few different elements. Instead of clicking on “create a new document” the user can click on “create glossary term”.

Climateurope2
PLATFORM

Search documents by type, author, name | My Profile

About | Actions | Contact | Feedback

Co-create > Document > Create

New document

With just a few easy clicks, you can begin a journey of teamwork, sharing your document with other colleagues.

Let's start

1 Fill the information required | 2 Collect feedback | 3 Publish

Document information

Document title *

Author
You will be the author of this document.

Co-Authors

Abstract *

Unit of Analysis * ⓘ

Document Type *

CE2 Project Objectives *

Spatial Domain *

Team information

Collaborators

Document privacy * ⓘ
 Open to collaborators
 Open to all

Priority ⓘ

Status ⓘ

Notes for feedback ⓘ

- Enter notes for feedback

Add more feedback (Enter) +

Upload new attachment

Use the input below to upload a new file for this document. It'll automatically increment the version if a document has been uploaded previously.

Upload your document by dragging and dropping it here, or click to browse and select a file from your device.

Post for collaboration >

Figure 14 - Climateurope2 Platform upload form.

- The member should check the document's status periodically to see if any feedback or comments have been added by other users and respond to any comments or feedback as needed. The member can use the platform's collaboration tools (e.g. chat, comments, annotations) to communicate with colleagues and make revisions. Once the (co)author has incorporated the feedback and made necessary revisions, a new version of the document can be uploaded via the form above. Comments on the draft documents can be placed by collaborators or (co)authors.

The screenshot shows the 'Climateurope2 PLATFORM' interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'About', 'Actions', 'Contact', and 'Feedback'. The breadcrumb trail indicates the document is in the 'Discussion' phase of a 'Co-create' process. A progress bar shows three steps: '1. Fill the information required', '2. Collect feedback', and '3. Publish', with the current step being '2. Collect feedback'. A notification states 'Your document has been created! Continue editing it below.'

The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column, titled 'Key Info', contains metadata for the document:

- Author:** Tjerk Krijger, Project Engineer, MARIS, Netherlands
- DOI:** No DOI assigned
- Upload date:** 2025 Jul 24
- Last update:** 2025 Jul 24 14:07
- Priority:** Medium
- Status:** In progress
- Tags:** Climate Services as a whole, Best Practices
- Spatial Domain:** European
- Version:** V1
- Source:** No source provided
- Uploaded versions:** Version #1: Guidelines for Using Seasonal Climate Outlooks in Agricultural Planning.pdf
- Actions:** Edit, Download, Discuss, Share
- Notes for feedback:** No notes for feedback provided.

The right column, titled 'Document', displays the document's title and abstract:

Guidelines for Using Seasonal Climate Outlooks in Agricultural Planning

Abstract
This document provides guidance on the effective use of seasonal climate outlooks to support agricultural decision-making in Southern Europe. It targets farmers, cooperatives, agri-advisors, and regional policymakers aiming to incorporate climate information into operational planning.

[Click here to read the complete version](#)

The document content includes:

- Guidelines for Using Seasonal Climate Outlooks in Agricultural Planning**
- Focus:** Southern Europe / Sector: Agriculture
- 1. Purpose:** This document provides guidance on the effective use of seasonal climate outlooks to support agricultural decision-making in Southern Europe. It targets farmers, cooperatives, agri-advisors, and regional policymakers aiming to incorporate climate information into operational planning.
- 2. Background:** Seasonal climate outlooks offer probabilistic forecasts of temperature and precipitation anomalies for the coming 1-6 months. They are key components of climate services under the Global Framework for Climate Services (GFCs) and are increasingly used in agriculture to manage risk and improve resilience to climate variability.
- 3. Scope of the Outlooks:**
 - Geographical coverage:** Mediterranean agricultural zones of Spain, Italy, Greece, and Portugal
 - Temporal coverage:** Monthly updates with lead times up to 6 months
 - Variables included:**
 - Precipitation (total and anomaly)
 - Temperature (mean, maximum, and anomaly)

Below the document content is a 'Discussion' section with a 'New comment' button and a 'Ready to publish' button. A comment box is visible with the text 'Start writing your comment here...'. The footer includes the European Union logo, funding information, and the Climateurope2 logo.

Figure 15 - Climateurope2 Platform co-create entry detail page.

- If the document is approved by the collaborators and (co)authors, it can be published, so that other members can see the final version.

Climateurope2
PLATFORM

Search documents by type, author, name

My Profile

About Actions Contact Feedback

Co-create > Guidelines for using seasonal climate outloo...

1 Fill the information required 2 Collect feedback 3 Publish

Document information

Document title *
Guidelines for Using Seasonal Climate Outlooks in Agricultural Plan

Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
Automatically generated once published.

Author *
Tjerk Krijger

Co-Authors

Abstract *
This document provides guidance on the effective use of seasonal climate outlooks to support agricultural decision-making in Southern Europe. It targets farmers, cooperatives, agri-advisors, and regional policymakers aiming to incorporate climate information into operational planning.

Unit of Analysis *
Climate Services as a whole x

Document Type *
Best Practices x

Objectives *
Developing standardisation procedures for climate services x

Spatial Domain *
European x

Previous version of this document

Upload new attachment

Use the input below to upload a new file for this document. It'll automatically increment the version if a document has been uploaded previously.

Previously uploaded versions

- Version #1: [Guidelines for Using Seasonal Climate Outlooks in Agricultural Planning.pdf](#)

Upload your document by dragging and dropping it here, or click to browse and select a file from your device.

Publish document

Funded by the European Union

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Figure 16 - Climateurope2 Platform publishing of documents.

5. The document is now made available for everyone to see in the documents section.

Climateurope2 PLATFORM

Search documents by type, author, name

My Profile

About Actions Contact Feedback

> All Documents

See all documentation

Our document section is a valuable resource for anyone seeking to stay up-to-date on the latest research and developments in climate services. Here, you can find a wide range of documents, including guidelines, vocabulary, reports, papers, and presentations, all of which are available for download.

Glossary

See our expanding list of climate related terms.

Explore >

Training

Browse our training materials.

Explore >

Key messages

The annual Climateurope2 synthesis report.

Explore >

Found 5 document(s).

Filters

Search by author

Search by unit of analysis

Search by document type

Search by spatial domain

Reset filters

	<p>Guidelines for Using Seasonal Climate Outlooks in Agricultural Planning</p> <p>Tjerk Krijger 2025-07-24</p> <p>Best Practices Climate Services as a whole</p>
	<p>Governance tools identified in Deliverable D2.1</p> <p>X Domingo 2025-02-22</p> <p>Reports Delivery mode and evaluation</p>
	<p>List of governance tools related to Artificial Intelligence.</p> <p>X Domingo 2025-01-20</p> <p>Others Delivery mode and evaluation</p>
	<p>Climate services components identified by Climateurope2</p> <p>Marina Baldissera Pacchetti 2024-09-24</p> <p>Best Practices Others Climate Services as a whole Standards</p>
	<p>Climateurope2 Glossary</p> <p>Saioa Zorita 2024-09-24</p> <p>Glossary Climate Services as a whole</p>

Figure 17 - Climateurope2 Platform document page with new document added.

3 Next steps

While the core components of the Climateurope2 platform have been implemented, a few small modifications are still foreseen to improve usability and functionality based on feedback that is received on the platform.

The main focus is now toward expanding engagement with the platform: this includes encouraging broader user participation and enriching the platform with additional documents. Some materials developed by the other WPs have already been uploaded, but more content is required to ensure the platform is sufficiently populated before its public launch during the Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade on the 30th of September, where a dedicated interactive session will introduce the platform and demonstrate its functionalities.

To support this uptake, a collaborative process is organised where:

1. The platform and coordination team select the Deliverables that have relevant material for uploading to the platform.
2. Of those Deliverables, the authors are contacted and a meeting with each author and the platform/coordination team is set-up for short guidance on the platform submission steps, to find their way through the platform and answer any questions they might have.
3. Each Deliverable author will be responsible for:
 - a. Uploading the executive summary of the Deliverable to the platform;
 - b. Identifying which outputs can and should be uploaded. This can cover extracts, small portions, few pages, sections from Deliverables covering guidelines, standards, good/best practices or reports. The actual work of compacting this information can be transferred to other people. It is important to share here with the author a clear description of what type of documents are expected.
4. Clear contribution targets, with each author expected to upload the executive summary before the CE2 Festival and a certain number of additional extracts from the Deliverable before the end of the year.
5. Progress visibility, with each new upload highlighted in the weekly report.